

ANALYSIS OF BRACING SYSTEMS ON THE FREE VIBRATION BEHAVIOR OF A PULTRUDED COMPOSITE COOLING TOWER

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ABSTRACT

Cooling towers are industrial equipment characterized by heavy components, large wind obstruction area and elevated humidity. High mechanical strength, low specific mass and great durability of pGFRP make it suitable for this type of structures, but little is found in scientific literature about their structural performance. The low modulus of elasticity of pGFRP makes the structures more flexible, susceptible to large displacements and vibration. This work assesses the contribution of two bracing systems to the free vibration behavior of a pGFRP cooling tower, aiming to increase its stiffness and avoid resonance due to low frequency loads such as wind fluctuation.

KEYWORDS

Pultruded GFRP structures; Cooling towers; Dynamics; Numerical simulation.

INTRODUCTION

The use of pultruded glass fiber reinforced polymer (pGFRP) profiles is a growing alternative to conventional materials like steel and wood. The main characteristics of pGFRP are high mechanical strength, low specific mass and great durability, which lead to resistant, light and easily assembled structures. Civil engineering applications of pGFRP go from secondary structures like ladders, handrails and walkways to main elements of bridges, footbridges and cooling towers (Correia, 2015; Qureshi, 2022).

Cooling towers are heat exchanger equipment that, by means of evaporative cooling, reduce the temperature of water from industrial processes. The cooling capacity required by industrial facilities results in structures with a large area of wind obstruction and large dead loads from components and the water. High mechanical properties and the environmental resistance of pGFRP profiles makes them well-suited for the very humid environment of a cooling tower, ensuring high durability and low maintenance costs (Boroujeni, 2011).

Although very resistant, pGFRP has a low modulus of elasticity compared to steel, which makes service limit states (SLS) determinant for structural design (Mendes et al., 2011). It also has a significant impact on the dynamic behavior of pGFRP structures, leading to higher flexibility and lower natural frequencies (Boscato et al., 2015; Boscato & Ientile, 2018). A good way to increase the structural stiffness and to reduce vibrations is with the use of bracings (Casalegno & Russo, 2015; Bahtiar et al., 2018). The efficiency of a bracing system depends on its spatial configuration (Razak et al., 2018; Azevedo et al., 2023), and higher stiffness can be found for full-length patterns like the double diagonal (X) and inverted-V (Yu et al., 2015).

This study presents the overall design concepts of a pGFRP cooling tower structure and assesses the contribution of the two aforementioned bracing systems to the structure's free vibration behavior, aiming to increase its natural frequency and avoid resonance due to dynamic wind loads.

DESIGN CONCEPTS

The cooling tower was designed as an 18 m wide and 9.2 m tall pGFRP frame structure. The column layout is shown in Fig. 1. Beams were placed in four levels, and beam spacing was based on the

maximum span of the cooling tower components. Fig. 2 shows a section of the cooling tower with beam top levels and component locations.

Figure 1: Column layout (dimensions in m).

Figure 2: Cooling tower section.

From the first to the third level, beams carry the weight of 55 m^3 of water, a 2 m tall PVC fill and a water distribution system (WDS) composed by a DN 900 glass fiber reinforced polymer (GFRP) main pipe, DN 150 PVC branch pipes and plastic spraying nozzles. The fourth level supports a pGFRP fan stack and guard rail, PVC drift eliminators, a 10.36 m diameter fan, a 220 kW motor and a 4 m tall pGFRP fan stack. Vertical components like the air inlet grid and casing panels, also made of GFRP, were assumed to be attached directly to the columns with specific brackets. The weights of the components were obtained from manufacturers, and the dead loads on the cooling tower are shown in Tab. 1. A maintenance live load of 2 kN/m^2 was defined based on Brazilian standard NBR 6120 (ABNT, 1980) and applied over the deck. Static wind load was calculated based on NBR 6123 (ABNT, 1988) for a structure located in Rio de Janeiro.

Table 1: Cooling tower dead loads.

Load source	Total load (kN)	Load location
Water	540	Levels 1, 2 and 3
Fill	118	Level 1
WDS main pipe	7.22	Level 2
WDS branch pipes	7.02	Level 3
Spraying nozzles	0.49	
Deck	19.6	Level 4
Guard rail	2.82	
Drif eliminator	33.6	
Fan	46.6	
Fan stack	46.7	
Motor	16.2	
Air inlet grid	18.1	Exterior columns
Casing panels	10.6	

While I-section beams and columns are most used in steel structures, pGFRP cooling towers are often built with back-to-back double-channel beams and square tube columns. This allows the beams to be continuous and eccentrically connected to the columns with a single bolt, contributing to a fast and easy assembly. Profile length was limited to 12 m due to transportation constraints, and beams were spliced in factors of that length whenever possible. Small segments of square tubes were placed at the middle of each span to work as a batten for the built up section (Fig. 3a). I-beams were used for short spacings, with dropped girders transferring their loads to the columns (Fig. 3b). At the perimeter of the structure, single channels were used on the inside face of the columns.

Figure 3: Beam and column details.

Profile sizes and material properties of the pGFRP were obtained from Fiberline Composites (2002), and a specific mass of $1,800 \text{ kg/m}^3$ was assumed. Tab. 2 shows the mechanical properties, where E_L is the longitudinal modulus of elasticity, E_t the transversal modulus of elasticity, G the shear modulus, f_t the tensile strength, f_c the compression strength, f_v the shear strength, $\nu_{90^\circ, 0^\circ}$ the major and $\nu_{0^\circ, 90^\circ}$ the minor Poisson's ratio. Fig. 4 shows profile dimensions, where the first index refers to beams (B), columns (C) or bracings (b), and the second index refers to profile shape (I-section, channel or square tube).

Table 2: Mechanical properties of pGFRP.

E_L (GPa)	E_t (GPa)	G (GPa)	f_t (MPa)	f_c (MPa)	f_v (MPa)	$v_{90^\circ, 0^\circ}$	$v_{0^\circ, 90^\circ}$
24.0	10.0	3.0	240	240	40	0.23	0.09

Figure 4: Profile dimensions in mm.

Two bracing configurations were analyzed: the double diagonal (X) and the inverted-V. Bracing members were slightly offset from columns' ends to avoid intersecting perpendicular beams (Fig. 5a). Connection to the columns was made with pGFRP bolted plates, and square tubes with the same dimensions of the columns were used for the bracing. This allows the bracing members to fit through the double-channel beams and serve as additional battens (Fig. 5b).

a) X and inverted-V-bracing systems, with detail for the offset connection at the end of column.

b) Bracing connection with pGFRP plates and additional battening of the beam.

Figure 5: Bracing configuration and connections.

Six rows of bracing were assigned parallel to the structure's X-axis and four parallel to the Y-axis, as shown in Fig. 6. This is due to the arrangement of components within the cooling tower, which makes some parts of the structure need more bracing to ensure stability. An example is in gridlines 4 and 5, where a close set of braces was placed near the water-filled main pipe, one of the most massive components. Besides providing stiffness where it's most needed, the different spacing in each direction avoids vertical intersections between bracing members that have crossing horizontal projections.

Figure 6: Bracing layout with a highlight on main pipe location.

NUMERICAL MODELING

A three dimensional model of the structure was developed in SAP2000 v.14.0.0, a commercial software based on the finite element method. Frame elements were used to model beams, columns and bracings. Rigid link elements with released rotational stiffnesses were used to simulate the pin behavior of bolted joints and the eccentricity of channel beams in relation to column axes (Fig. 7).

Figure 7: Modeling of beam-column bolted joints.

All supports were considered pinned. The masses of components were assigned to the frame elements to represent their contribution to the free vibration response of the structure. Vertical load from casing panels and horizontal wind loads were applied directly to the exterior columns, and the loads from other components were applied to the beams as shown in Fig. 8. A 3D view of the X-braced model is shown in Fig. 9 with a color legend for the profiles.

Figure 8: Examples of load application to the model.

Figure 9: 3D view of the X-braced model.

STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

Ultimate limit state (ULS) and service limit state (SLS) verifications were carried out based on the Brazilian pre-standard for the design of pGFRP structures (ABNT, 2023), with load combinations from NBR 8681 (ABNT, 2004). Tab. 3 shows the verification of bending ULS and beam deflection SLS for the unbraced structure, where M_{Sd} is the required bending moment, M_{Rd} the bending resistance, L is the length of the beam and δ is the deflection at midspan. The deflection limit was set to $L/250$.

Table 3: Bending ULS and beam deflection SLS verification for the unbraced structure.

Profile	M_{Sd} (kNm)	M_{Rd} (kNm)	M_{Sd}/M_{Rd} (%)	L (m)	δ (mm)
B-I-1	1.03	6.59	15.6	1.18	1.0 (L/1193)
B-I-2	2.92	14.0	20.8	0.34	0.8 (L/444)

B-C-1	1.19	4.17	28.6	2.75	2.4 (L/1165)
B-C-2	4.82	16.3	29.5	0.42	3.7 (L/267)
B-C-3	7.25	60.2	12.0	1.34	3.8 (L/262)

It can be seen from Tab. 3 that required bending strengths didn't exceed 30% of the profiles' resistant capacities, and the static design of the most required beam profiles (B-I-2, B-C-2 and B-C-3) was conditioned by deflection SLS.

Tab. 4 shows the first results of free vibration analysis for the unbraced, X-braced and inverted-V-braced frames, where f_n is the natural frequency of the n-th vibration mode, φ_n is its mode shape and M is the total mass of the structure. The first mode shape of each model is shown in Fig. 10 to 12.

Table 4: Free vibration analysis results.

Model	f_1 (Hz)	φ_1	f_2 (Hz)	φ_2	f_3 (Hz)	φ_3	M (kg)
Unbraced	0.31	Bending in X	0.42	Bending in Y	0.47	Torsion	14,450
X-braced	1.22	Bending in Y	1.32	Bending in Y	1.33	Bending in Y	17,550
Inverted-V-braced	1.27	Bending in Y	1.28	Bending in Y	1.29	Bending in Y	17,420

Figure 10: First mode shape of the unbraced frame (bending in X direction).

Figure 11: First mode shape of the X-braced frame (bending in Y direction).

Figure 12: First mode shape of the inverted-V-braced frame (bending in Y direction).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The pGFRP frame showed very low natural frequencies for the unbraced configuration. This result was expected because, in addition to the low modulus of elasticity of the material, all joints were considered flexible. According to NBR 6123 (ABNT, 1988), structures with a natural frequency lower than 1 Hz should be dynamically analyzed for the possibility of resonance due to wind fluctuation. The cooling tower has a large wind obstruction area and the first vibration modes occur in wind direction, so it's expected that dynamic wind load would bring large displacements. Since the resistant capacity of the profiles is already underused, increasing the cross sections would be unnecessarily costly, and it becomes unfeasible to design this type of structure without a bracing system.

Both the X and the inverted-V bracing patterns showed excellent performance in stiffening the structure. Natural frequencies increased from two to four times, moving away from the range of frequencies most susceptible to resonance when subjected to dynamic wind loads. The natural frequencies obtained from each braced configuration were very similar (Tab. 4), as well as the mode shapes excited at those frequencies (Fig. 11 and 12). They involved bending in Y direction as a consequence of fewer bracing rows compared to X direction (Fig. 6).

An interesting result is that, while the unbraced structure presented torsion in its third vibration mode, the braced ones didn't show torsional modes. Mode shapes of braced structures involved global and local bending, showing that the bracing systems contribute to a higher torsional stiffness.

Regarding the total mass, inverted-V bracing was less than 1% lighter than X-bracing, showing again similar performances between both systems. The X-bracing might come up as a more economic option for requiring less connections and bearing points, but it's worth noting that a inverted-V bracing system spanning from side to side could lead to an even lighter braced structure.

This research showed that bracing systems are fundamental for pGFRP cooling tower structures. Since they are built with single-bolt connections with low rotational stiffness, these structures are very flexible, resulting in large deflections and low natural frequencies. The use of bracing systems improves their dynamic behavior and allows for a safe exposure to low frequency dynamic loads like wind fluctuation, while benefitting of the advantageous properties of pGFRP profiles.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.